

Asetu Himachalam

Asetu Himachalam (From Setu bridge to the Himalayas) is the official motto of the Survey of India, but perhaps it does not convey the full range of work and exploration by teams of specially trained surveyors and cartographers who were often ‘deputed’ to work with archaeologists, the military and others in South Asia but also as far as Malawi. An institution that was begun in 1767, out of the British imperial project of control which sought to better understand the landscape that it wished to control and tax. Furthered by the efforts of the Great Trigonometrical Survey project, the SoI aimed to measure, categorise and map the Indian Subcontinent, including but not limited to the modern countries of India, Pakistan, Burma, Nepal and adjacent areas.

The histories of the Survey of India are one meticulously recorded in **bureaucratic lists of expenses** and in **annual reports** of calculations and **landscape observations**. However, folded between the sheets of paper and read between the lines of these reports are glimpses into the **rarely recognised and forgotten personalities** of the Indians who travelled the length and breadth of the Indian Subcontinent and beyond.

While their European counterparts may have been lauded as **great explorers** and archaeologists in their time, it is only relatively recently that the stories of **Indian surveyors and archaeologists** are being brought to the forefront and being given their due credit. Though the names, words and experiences of many surveyors and subsurveyors may have slipped through the cracks over time, we do have stories of a few Indians as told through **letters, maps and awards** for their achievements. Though these surveyors have been called 'indigenous' in reality they were **travelling far from their homes** and encountering people and lands as different to them as they were to their foreign counterparts. Some of these explorations have been written in their own accounts.

Archaeology and Survey of India

For expeditions that were mounted in or started from India, **topographical surveys**, particularly in regions away from the main British centres of power, were important outcomes. As such, the **highly-trained native surveyors** were precious resources. They were often commodified and loaned or “deputised” from the SoI to scientific expeditions – **archaeological, zoological, geological** etc. In reality, the role of these surveyors on the field **almost always extended beyond the remit of surveying**, to being enablers and extensions of the expedition’s main aim. However, their contributions with these expeditions and their relationship to the colonial men they worked with, and often under, are difficult to trace.

Aurel Stein

For scholars of these “**hidden histories**”, archives of colonial men, particularly those who were assiduous in recording the contributions of the native surveyors are the first place to start. Previous works in this have revealed the **intricate dynamics** on the field between the European and the native members of expeditions.

The Hungarian-born, British archaeologist **Aurel Stein** was one such example, with his published works listing the works and contributions of his native associates in substantial detail. More significantly, his archives, held between the Stein Papers at the **Bodleian Library** and the **India Office Records (IOR)** at the **British Library**, provide a deeper, more personal view of these men.

He led expeditions to western China, Persia as well as the 'frontier' regions of colonial India.

“

In regard to the person of the surveyor I need scarcely point out that a man of good physique accustomed to travelling under somewhat difficult conditions would be likely to render better services in the territories to be visited. I must consider in this consideration also the high altitude of the Karakorum passes to be crossed on the way. A surveyor capable of making simple approximate observations with the sextant would be particularly useful

Aurel Stein

**SURVEYOR LAL SING AND RAI SAHIB AT WORK ON THE TOP OF LANAK LA,
17,750 FEET.**

Lal Singh

Lal Singh was a **Daffadar** (A nDaffadar). A native rank, equivalent to a sergeant in the British Indian army) with the **19th Bengal Lancers** until he joined the SoI in October 1895.

While it is unclear how Lal Singh was selected for the SoI, a discussion at the RGS gives an indication of the criteria for a native surveyor to be trained and deputed for particularly important expeditions both within and outside the borders of British India. According to this, it is a long and laborious process starting with **drafting well-educated Indian men who undergo basic training** and are further put through five to six years of "**severe training**" before they are deemed ready for expeditions. The quote below describes part of this process:

“

If you will for an instant consider what the process is by which men, such as those to whom Major Bruce has

alluded, arrive at the skill which they attain as surveyors, you will, I think, agree with me that it is a long process, and laborious process, to attain such an amount of technical knowledge as they acquire. In the first place, in India, the men whom we get for this duty are drafted from all sources, both civil and military; and you must remember that from the very beginning they are well-educated men. In India, having got the men specially selected, in the first instance, they are again subjected to a process which we might call a process of natural selection, until finally, after some years' experience, they are drafted into the Survey Department for a further five or six years' severe training before they can take the field for such work as Major Bruce has described. All this, as you will easily recognize, is a matter of time and patience and infinite trouble.

Surveyors were regularly sent on deputation on military campaigns, such as punitive expedition, the Tochi Field Force in 1897 on the

Afghan border that Lal Singh accompanied.

In the Footsteps of Lal Singh: A Surveyor's Journey

Esri, USGS | Esri, TomTom, FAO, NOAA, USGS

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1 Training

1897 Tochi Valley, Waziristan district, KPK. Also known as Dawar

Surveyors such as Lal Singh would have been sent on deputation to military expeditions such as the **Tochi Field Force** on the Afghan border.

This was brigade of British and Indian soldiers sent to the **Tochi Valley** to take punitive actions against rebelling Waziri tribes.

The surveyors were sent out to map the surrounding areas.

The true battle was with the heat, swarms of flies and dysentery..

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TWO SIXPENCE
WHOLE SHEETS 10 PENCE

1900-1901

Lal Singh conducted a route survey from Lorai Pass to Chitral and surveyed a large area on the 1/2 inch scale in the neighborhood of Chitral.

1902-1904

Lal Singh's talents were first highlighted for his work with the **Aden Boundary Commission**. The turn of the 20th century was a hotly contested one in the borderlands of the fast-crumbling Ottoman empire. In Feb 1902, surveyors from British India led by Col Wahab moved into the Adeni hinter-land to formally stake out the boundaries of territory claimed by Britain in South Arabia.

Of the surveyors, Lal Singh was appreciated the most and according to Capt Tandy, the officer in charge:

"More especially I should like to call to your notice the work of Surveyor Lall Singh, this man has been with the detachment during the whole 2 1/2 years of iuts work, on his has fallen the brunt of the plate-tabling and he has invariably carried it out

excellently. He is a thoroughly reliable and trustworthy surveyor and a man with whom it is a pleasure to work."

In Sep 1904 he was helping with the drawing of the maps from that survey, when the Sol headquarters required him to travel. In response, Captain Tandy complained:

"I should be very sorry indeed to part with Surveyor Lal Singh, at present unless his presence elsewhere is absolutely indispensable. There are many parts of the Aden country that Lal Singh alone has visited thus making it very important that he should be present when the fair drawing is taking place."

4 NWFP and Baluchistan with Stein

III. WALLS OF KĀFĪR-KŌṬ, SOUTH-WEST FACE.

1904-1905

Lal Singh's survey experience coincided with the British Indian government's archaeological projects in 1904, when he was deputed to accompany the Hungarian-

born British archaeologist **Aurel Stein** on an Archaeological Survey of the **North-West Frontier Province and Baluchistan** from Jan 2nd 1904 to March 31, 1905. This was a significant expedition both for the SoI and the ASI, since as Stein notes:

"Owing to its position in Tribal territory beyond the north-east border of the Peshawar District this hill tract had hitherto been inaccessible to Europeans, and had remained a terra incognita to the archaeologist as well as the topographer. The successful trans-border tour... has led to the discovery of several important sites and to the elucidation of questions of great interest for the history and ancient geography of Gandhara. It has served besides geographical interests, inasmuch as an area of over 200 square miles hitherto unsurveyed was carefully mapped under my supervision by Surveyor Rai Lal Singh."

5

Rai Sahib Title

Lal Singh was a much-sought-after and dedicated surveyor. On 29 Oct, 1904, Col Longe, the Surveyor General of India recommended Lal Singh for the title of **Rai Sahib**. As he noted in his letter:

"Lal Singh is one of a class of men of whom we have but too few at present in the Survey of India, keen trustworthy and intelligent, with a strong sense of duty and a spirit that cheerfully undertakes difficult and often dangerous work, the public recognition of his services will act as a stimulus to others and bring a better class of recruit to the Survey of India."

From the archives, we also know that the SoI had submitted a recommendation during the previous Delhi Durbar but had been returned since it was submitted too

late. In 1904, however, Lal Singh was awarded the title of Rai Sahib and he accepted it formally in July 1905, even incorporating the "RS" into his signature.

6 In the Footsteps of Marco Polo

Crossing the Ak-su-la, N.W. Thibet.

1905-1907

Captain Bruce Dalrymple travelled from Simla to Beijing, a journey that he documented in the book *In the Footsteps of Marco Polo* and also at the *Royal Geographical Society* in 1907. Like Capt Tandy earlier, Capt Bruce too was highly impressed with Lal Singh's dedication:

"The second, far the more arduous of the two objects, was only carried through thanks to the wonderful determination and pluck of our Indian surveyor, a Sikh, Lall Sing by name, lent by the Survey of India. To carry on such work as Lall Sing

did daily, with frequent night observations at altitudes over 16,000 feet in Northern Tibet so late in the year as the middle of October, moving nearly every day for nine months on end, is a feat which any man, even with the reputation which those who work for the Survey of India enjoy, may, I think you will well be proud."

In a telling anecdote Capt Bruce narrated:

"We had returned from a long day's survey of the lake, and Layard and myself were seated round the camp-fire taking a meal and congratulating ourselves upon a useful day's work. Lall Singh was putting the finishing touches to the map a few yards away. We suddenly heard him make some remark, but as he continued sketching we did not trouble to turn round. Again he spoke, and this time we caught his words, " Shikar arghir, sahib" ("something to shoot approaches"). Jumping up, we ran for the little .303, seeing at the same time three gazelle advancing apparently quite unconscious of us or the camp. Taking up a position behind Lall Singh's tent, I took the buck standing and knocked him over, then had a second barrel at the other beast as they cantered away, but missed. All this and more occurred within 100 yards of his tent, but I hardly think Lall Singh raised his eyes from his plane table. As he was when he so solemnly reported the arrival of the shikar, so he remained ten minutes later when Layard returned from bagging the one I had missed."

7

Stein's Second Expedition

1907-1908

By the time Lal Singh returned from the Capt Bruce expedition, Aurel Stein was on his **second Central Asian expedition**. However, the surveyor who had accompanied him, **Ram Singh** had to be invalided. Lal Singh was then chosen to replace him. This would be Lal Singh's first long-range archaeological expedition and multiple sources exist in the Stein Papers archive at the Bodleian Library, Oxford, that record Lal Singh's work in this period.

Not just traditional topographical surveys, Lal Singh understood what archaeological expeditions in Chinese Turkestan at the time entailed. On occasion, when he was away from the main caravan, surveying on his own, his letters to Stein indicate regular reports of spotting ruins, identifying suitable guides for Stein and even occasionally, purchasing antiques for Stein from the local villages he passed through.

8

RGS Back Grant

1909

When Stein was awarded the **Founder's Medal** by the **Royal Geographic Society (RGS)** in 1909, in recognition of his second expedition, Stein didn't forget to mention

the contribution of the surveyors. In fact, so impressive was this “cartographical harvest”, **Lal Singh was awarded the Back Grant the same year**, one of only four surveyors from SoI to have ever won an award or medal from the RGS. Incidentally, Stein had received the same award a mere four years earlier in 1904.

The citation for the award read, "*For admirable and faithful work as a surveyor, accompanied Dr Stein in his last journeys.*"

Lal Singh is recognized as: "*The admirable native surveyor who accompanied Dr. Stein on his last expedition. We hear from Dr. Stein that he showed not only great fitness for the work of a surveyor, but also exceptional zeal under trying circumstances. He had previously undertaken several expeditions from Yemen to Eastern China, whilst with Dr. Stein he carried plane-table surveys along the Tien-Shan to Kashgar, on the northern slopes of the Kunlun, and in other localities. We must all feel regret that Lal Singh is not here in person to receive our sincere congratulations.*" (TGJ:1909, Pg 101)

9

Rai Bahadur Title

1909

Lal Singh's contributions were recognised in India too, this time with a higher title of **Rai Bahadur**, evidently with the recommendation of Stein, through the secretary to the Viceroy, James Dunlop-Smith. On Lal Singh's title, Stein wrote to Dunlop-Smith,

"For Lal Singh, my devoted surveyor's 'Rai Bahadur' I am also chiefly indebted to you. I must feel doubly grateful for what you did on behalf of my faithful helpmates since the results of my explorations like those of my Turkestan journey of 1900-01 have never received a word of official acknowledgement."

This echoed what had earlier been expressed at the RGS,

"Sub-surveyors, all of whom are highly trained, are always ready to volunteer to accompany any British officer, or any Britisher, into no matter what parts of Central Asia. When the history of the exploration of Central Asia comes to be written, I sincerely hope we shall find adequate credit given to the Indian Government, and more especially the Survey Department of India, for all the valuable help and assistance they have given to geographical research and science in Central Asia." (Holdich & others:1907, Pg 624-625)

10 Islamabad – Srinagar

1912

There are no records in the archives that indicate Lal Singh's work between 1909 and 1912. In 1912, however, we know he was finishing computation in **Srinagar**, having completed triangulation till **Islamabad**. In a letter congratulating his Stein for his KCIE honour, he also relates that he is keeping busy with astronomical work at night and computation during the day.

11 Stein's Third Expedition

Halt at Buk [Buk-tokhal], Etsingol. Lal Singh] and Isa Bai, 13 June 1914. British Library, Photo 392/28 (530)

1913-1916

Soon after, Stein set out for his third Central Asian expedition with Lal Singh as his principal surveyor. Here again, Lal Singh was the reliable archaeological assistant in addition to his duties as the surveyor. The expedition was Stein's most successful, bringing away 182 cases on 80 camels, of archaeological finds. Most importantly, at the end of the expedition, Stein entrusted Lal Singh to bring back the archaeological finds to India while he himself proceeded to Persia. Stein relates this,

"The final arrangements were made for the long journey which by the middle of October brought the large convoy of 'archaeological proceeds' under the personal supervision of R. B. Lal Singh, safely to their temporary place of deposit at Srinagar. He was assisted in this task by Naik Shamsuddin and Surveyor Muhammad Yaqub, who also accompanied the collection to India. He was thus able to supplement our previous surveys by useful topographical work along the caravan route followed across the Yangi-dawan and by the uppermost Yarkand river to the Indian frontier on the Karakoram pass." (Stein:1928, Vol 2, Pg 843-844)

1917

For his contribution to Stein's 3rd Central Asian expedition, Lal Singh was awarded the **Murchinson Grant** by the **Royal Geographical Society**, the only surveyor from India to have received it. His citation read: *For his excellent work as surveyor to the last Trans-Himalayan expedition of Sir Aurel Stein.*

At the time of the award, the president of the RGS noted,

"Lal Singh has spent many years in trans-frontier survey, with Sir Aurel Stein in 1904, with Colonel Bruce in 1905 and 1906, and again with Sir Aurel Stein in 1907. For these services he was awarded the Back Grant by the Society in 1909. Sir Aurel Stein tells me that it was owing mainly to Lal Singh's unremitting exertions in his third expedition in 1913-1916 that the surveys could be extended over many hundred square miles of difficult mountain country in the face of most trying physical conditions. Whenever practicable Lal Singh travelled by independent routes, and by his work the Indian triangulation was extended along the Kun-lun range beyond Lopnor and across the Lop desert to the Central Tien-shan. We are

glad to learn that his services have been rewarded, on his approaching retirement from the Survey of India, with a grant of irrigated land."

13

Dehradun

L. A. S.

When I had the pleasure of seeing you on my last visit to you town I spoke to you about the exceptionally hard & highly useful survey work which my old travel companion R. B. Lal Singh had carried on during my C.A. expedition of 1913-15 and told you how glad I should feel if the R.G.S. could accord it recognition in a suitable way by the award of one of its annual grants. You were kind enough to offer to put his claims before the Council when the time came and as this date for considering the awards must be drawing in I am anxious to avail myself of your friendly help in the matter. I feel, I ought to not to trouble you with too long a letter, for on the one hand the essential facts about L. S. services are already on record in the preliminary account of our explorations which Geog. J.

1919

In late 1919, Lal Singh's stellar record earned him a **6-month extension at the Survey**.

As he prepared for his life post-retirement, he applied to the government to be granted the post of the **magistrate** in his native town **Gujranwala**. Despite the troubles in Punjab following the Jallianwallah Bagh massacre, Stein was able to add his weight to Lal Singh's application and even got the two successive governors of Punjab, Michael O'Dwyer and Maclagan to get behind it. In addition, the Punjab government also granted a **substantial jagir**, thus securing income not just for Lal Singh but for three subsequent generations.

14

Gujranwala

Having retired in February, Lal Singh was appointed **magistrate in Gujranwala**. He went on to build a sprawling haveli in Gujranwala and a farm in his village Nurpur. His great-grandson Stephen Sander recalls having camels and horses and large stables at home.

Lal Singh died at the age of 78 at his home in 1938. He was survived by his wife and six children.

Rai Bahadur Lal Singh's remarkable contributions to the fields of Surveying and Archaeology stand as a testament to his dedication, expertise, and pioneering spirit. His work with the Survey of India and the Archaeological Survey of India, particularly with his dear friend Aurel Stein, advanced the scientific and geographical understanding of many regions, ranging from Yemen, South Asia, the 'Northern Frontier', and extending into China. Lal Singh's legacy as a surveyor is one of precision, perseverance, and an unyielding commitment to expanding the boundaries of knowledge, tied to a love for exploring and recording challenging terrains.

Although remarkable, Lal Singh's story is not unique. The archives of the Survey of India hold many stories of adventurous, dedicated Surveyors and Sub-Surveyors, *if only we take care to look in the margins.*

Rai Bahadur Lal Singh with camels, Yolchi-moinak, 19th July 1915.

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